

OPEN SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION IN THE EUROPEAN
RESEARCH AREA FOR SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES
- PREPARATION

WP1: Project Management and Technical
coordination
D1.1 Collaborative web platform

Deliverable 1.1
Collaborative web platform

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I. Introduction

The « collaborative web platform » hereby describes the communication tools and means used by the participants of the OPERAS-P project for general internal communication, for coordination and management of the task implementation and for file sharing and storage. This document also constitutes a user guide for the Work Package (WP) leaders and participants.

For OPERAS-P project internal communication, 5 main tools will be used: a mailing list, Google Drive, Mattermost, Zoom, and Trello.

Different aspects of the communication between participants will be addressed in this document :

- Internal communication within the OPERAS-P project.
- Sharing, sending, storing and organising of the files related to the project.
- Common policies regarding the management of the files.
- Use of a project management tool for up-to-date information.

II. Internal communication

A. Mailing lists

Mailing lists allow their subscribers to communicate between them within a formal framework of the project. The messages might concern the internal communication of the project, as for instance general meetings, announcement or communication of the meeting's minutes, project changes request and approval or any global issue that might influence the financial and administrative implementation of the project.

A mailing list has been created for the OPERAS-P project on the French public research communication network, RENATER (<https://groupes.renater.fr/>). The email address of the list is operas-p@groupes.renater.fr. It allows any subscriber to receive and write messages from and to the "OPERAS-P" list.

B. Google Drive

1. Storage

A specific folder has been created on Google Drive for the OPERAS-P project, unequivocally named “OPERAS-P” and with a tree-structure based on the various WPs. OPERAS-P folder has seven subfolders corresponding to the seven WPs. Each subfolder in turn is divided into as many subfolders as tasks.

Here’s the link to the folder:

https://drive.google.com/drive/u/0/folders/1TZOz07ZSer_HGU_NTFvo9KjH4j123Ghc

Under the responsibility of the PMT, if not already done by the WP leaders or the participants, the stable or final versions of the files have to be integrated to the related folder.

In order to assure minimal backup policy, at least the final version of a deliverable has to be deposited both on Mattermost and on Google Drive.

A. Files format

Google doc sharing should always be preferred to sending document to review by email. Only finalised versions should be sent by email. Other formats should only be used for specific editing or styling work.

B. Files versioning

Google Drive automatically register the modifications. For this reason, and to facilitate the reviewing by the participants, files will not be versioned within the OPERAS-P project.

Only the version sent to the H2020 Participant’s Portal will be marked “final draft” in its name.

C. File naming policies

Every file added to the OPERAS-P project and related to a WP should abide to some naming policies. This will facilitate the retrieval from the various tools used by the project (Google Drive, e-mail).

It’s better to avoid spaces in the file names. It’s possible to connect the different parts with underscores or dashes. When doing so, each word must be in lowercase. Another possibility is to use the camel case.

The filename should give some minimal information so that it can be easily identified and retrieved. Minimal information is:

- a code referring to the project, the WP and the task;

- the subject or title.

The file naming pattern will be the following (within brackets is the variable part):

OP [WP number.Task number] - [producer] - [subject] - ... (_final draft)

Details:

1. "OP" for OPERAS-P project
2. Number of the Work Package (1, 2, 3,...)
3. Number of the task (1, 2, 3,...)
4. Producer (acronym of the participant: EKT, OE, MWS,...)
5. Subject section: a few words, connected with underscore or dashes
6. (Final version mention)

Examples :

OP1.1-OE-collaborative-platform_final draft

D. Mattermost

For former projects (HIRMEOS, OPERAS-D) and for the whole OPERAS community (working groups), Slack platform has been used to manage instant communication channels. Despite its efficiency, Slack proved to be unsustainable in the long term for us: the costs are too high, CNRS considers them as uneligible by the EC, and Slack software is proprietary. Thanks to Huma-Num effort, we decided to use [Mattermost](#) which is the open source software equivalent to Slack, hosted by our partner Huma-Num. The previous channels we were using for the OPERAS community have also been migrated from Slack to Mattermost.

E. Trello

The PMT gathers all the information about the on-going tasks in the project management web tool *Trello*. Those information are accessible to all partners of the project. Work Package leaders and Task leaders can use it to their convenience to manage their on-going work.

The OPERAS-P Trello URL is:

<https://trello.com/invite/b/dLAtQJR4/a947ca0615fe6e157297caa3514a5dbf/operas-p>.

Trello (<https://trello.com>) allows its subscribers to create boards (for specific missions) containing cards (the various tasks of the mission). Cards can have

checklists, e.g. the phases of the task. They can also have “due dates”, e.g. the due dates of the deliverables.

In the case of OPERAS-P, boards correspond to each WP and the cards correspond to the tasks of the WP.

F. Zoom

During former projects, Slack was used for video conference. For the financial reasons enumerated above (see Mattermost), we decided to use another tool for this project. We decided to use the video conference tool Zoom (<https://www.zoom.us/>). We chose this tool for its efficiency, and because it could be easily used by our partners. Indeed, some of our partners already use Zoom accounts in their infrastructure (Huma-Num, DARIAH, IBL-PAN). In this distributed perspective, corresponding to the reality of a European infrastructure such as OPERAS, we opted to use those accounts for the needs of the project. For instance, our partner DARIAH created one account for the OPERAS Coordination Team (as part of T3.1 Support to Core Group), and other professional accounts are due to be created.

III. Annexes

A. Google Drive

B. Mattermost migration procedure

As this service is new for our partners, we propose here the procedure to register in Mattermost:

First, you will need to create an account to be able to use Mattermost, this account can be created by logging in via eduGAIN, ORCID, other accounts or created from scratch. Note: Please use the same email address as you use for the Slack channel, if you were using it. The page where this is possible is <https://humanid.huma-num.fr>. This page might be in french by default, please click the english flag to change the language (See Image 1 and 2).

Image 1: <https://humanid.huma-num.fr> - French page (See the flags at the bottom of the page)

Image 2: <https://humanid.huma-num.fr> - English page

Once logged in, you will see a page presenting you some of the different service of Huma-Num, including Mattermost (See Image 3).

Manage my Huma-Num services

<p>GitLab, the complete DevOps platform</p> <p>askService</p>	
<p>Team Discussion Service</p> <p>Access</p>	

Image 3: Once logged in, view of some Huma-Num services including Mattermost - please click “askService” for Mattermost.

(On this screenshot the access was already provided so the button says “Access” instead)

Click on the “askService” button for Mattermost. This will send you to a page where you will need to provide the name of the Teams you want to be part of - depending

on the projects you take part in, you will need to enter “**OPERAS-P**” if you are a member (See Image 4).

If you forget this part, the administrators will still be able to add you to the correct Teams.

This step will take a little while because the Huma-Num team will need to approve this request manually, once they do, you will receive an email confirmation.

A screenshot of a web interface showing a modal dialog box titled "Demande d'accès au service Mattermost". The dialog contains the text "Merci de renseigner les informations suivantes :". Below this, there are two input fields. The first is labeled "Affiliation *" and contains the text "DARIAH". The second is labeled "Equipe(s) à rejoindre ou à créer *" and contains the text "OPERAS". At the bottom right of the dialog, there are two buttons: "askService" and "Close". The background of the page is dimmed and shows a Mattermost chat interface with a sidebar containing "Team Discussion Service" and a main area with a "askService" button.

Image 4: Add your affiliation and the Teams you want to join (“**OPERAS**”, “**OPERAS-P**” and/or “**TRIPLE**”)

Once you receive the confirmation, you will be able to connect to Mattermost on <https://chatting.huma-num.fr/> and when you are connected you will see the page below (See Image 5).

Image 5: When accessing Mattermost on <https://chatting.huma-num.fr/> (directly in Browser or via the Desktop Mattermost application), the default language might be french.

As you can see, the page might be in french by default, so the next steps are to show you how to switch it to english (Image 6, 7 and 8).

Image 6: To change to english follow the description and screenshots, here click on your username and select “Paramètres du compte”.

Image 7: In the menu select “Affichage”, and at the bottom of the page, you will see “Langue”, please click “Modifier”.

Image 8: In the dropdown, select “English”, and do not forget to save the modifications. When doing so, the page will reload and the interface will be in english.

Once you are logged in, have the screen in english (or you chosen language), then you can click on “More...” below the “Public Channels” and join the different channels you are interested in or belong to (See Image 9).

If you are willing to create a channel that you think deserves to be created and which doesn't exist yet, please click on the “+” button next to the “Public Channels” (See Image 9). You can create public or private channels, but they can not be modified once created.

Image 9: English view, with links “More...” to join existing channels and “+” to create channels.

Here are some extra information that might be useful:

Link for HumanID (Login for Huma-Num): <https://humanid.huma-num.fr/>

Link for Mattermost: <https://chatting.huma-num.fr/>

Link to download Mattermost Desktop:

<https://mattermost.com/download/#mattermostApps>

And here are the contacts of the administrators of the different Teams run by OPERAS:

- OPERAS: yoann.moranville@dariah.eu
- OPERAS-P: paulin.ribbe@openedition.org

C. Trello

The screenshot shows a Trello board titled "OPERAS-P" with a "Privé" (Private) status. The board is organized into four columns representing different work packages (WPs):

- WP2 ESFRI application**:
 - T2.1 Vision statement
 - T2.2 OPERAS Strategic plan
 - T2.3 Stakeholders and Users
 - T2.4 Impact and sustainability
 - T2.5 Governance and human resources
 - T2.6 E-needs
 - + Ajouter une autre carte
- WP3 Support to OPERAS RI**:
 - T3.1 Support to OPERAS Coordination Team
 - T3.2 Support to AISBL: preparation implementation and operational phase
 - T3.3 Support to the Core Group
 - + Ajouter une autre carte
- WP4 Transnational access to publication services**:
 - T4.1 Common access point to services
 - T4.2 User Authentication Implementation
 - T4.3 Standards mapping and adoption (including Interoperability between publishing services)
 - T4.4 Management of OPERAS infrastructure user communities
 - T4.5 Integration in the EOSC portal
 - + Ajouter une autre carte
- WP5 Redevelopment of DOAB as OPERAS central service**:
 - T5.1 Requirements and specifications
 - T5.2 Development of system
 - T5.3 Migration to D-space
 - + Ajouter une autre carte